

UNLOCKING DATA

Canada

LEARNING BRIEF

HOW CAN WE HARNESS SUB-NATIONAL GOVERNANCE TO SCALE THE USES AND USERS OF EDUCATION DATA?

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Authors: Charles Gachoki, Esme Kadzamira, Rigobert Pambe

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About this document

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About the Unlocking Data Initiative

The Unlocking Data Initiative is a community of practice that connects African scholars, NGOs, national statistics offices, and policymakers to improve access to and use of education data. The **Unlocking Data: Scaling Uses and Users of Education Data** project is a collaborative effort led by Zizi Afrique Foundation and supported by Education Sub-Saharan Africa, eBase Africa, and the University of Malawi's Centre for Education Research and Training (CERT). The latter project, which is being implemented in Cameroon, Kenya, and Malawi, aims to scale up the use of data and its users to address the knowledge gap on how to adaptively scale up the effective use of existing education data by policymakers and researchers in Africa.

To learn more about us, visit <https://unlockingdata.africa/>. Our evidence library can be found at <https://docs.unlockingdata.africa/lib/>

Why working with the subnational level matters

The middle tier, often called the subnational level of governance, includes lower units responsible for education administration, governance, and management, such as regional, county, district, and ward levels. Despite its critical role in education governance, this level is often underused in scaling innovative solutions, especially in education. While central governments establish policies and schools implement them, it is the middle tier that serves as a bridge, translating policies into local actions and ensuring innovations are adopted, supported, and sustained.

Leveraging the knowledge, expertise, and proximity of the middle tier is essential for any strategy seeking large-scale systemic improvement. The middle tier is not just an administrative layer but a vital leverage point for transforming education systems because it connects policy and practice at lower levels and the classroom; their experience is crucial for scaling innovations, thanks to their local knowledge and expertise accumulated over years; it offers instructional leadership and supports teachers; collects data, monitors progress, and provides feedback; ensures accountability and promotes equity; maintains impact through local ownership; coordinates external assistance; holds great potential for low-cost, high-impact innovations; and forms the foundation of system resilience and adaptability.

A dependable, functional ecosystem for foundational learning data is crucial for effective policymaking, planning, and resource allocation. This brief explores the challenges affecting this foundation at the middle-tier or subnational level in Kenya, Malawi, and Cameroon. Major issues include a general lack of analytical skills and skilled personnel, problems with data manipulation, insecure and fragmented storage systems, and persistent gaps in data quality and sharing. These issues manifest as (i) the need for dashboard and tool harmonization in Kenya; (ii) collection of cohort tracking data that does not reach the national level in Malawi; (iii) the perception of the middle tier as merely data collectors rather than users; and (iv) in Cameroon, the necessity to build trust and consensus through pre-consultations before collective subnational efforts can succeed.

These issues stem from inadequate capacity, poor coordination, and a non-data-driven culture. To transform this landscape, the brief highlights a four-pillar collaborative intervention: (1) establishing a centralised, secure data repository; (2) launching a comprehensive capacity-building program; (3) institutionalising formal data-sharing protocols; and (4) prioritising investment in data personnel and technology.

In practice, these pillars translate into: Kenya strengthening subnational data use through linking data points at the subnational level through harmonised tools and

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indicators, leveraging on the Education Evidence for Action (EE4A) forum that links researchers with academia and policymakers, and building the capacity of the government officers to increase demand for data and evidence, learning from the Malawi Open Data for Education Systems Analysis (MODESA) project to increase the use of existing data to generate evidence and digitising cohort tracking with DHIS2-aligned technical support, and Cameroon building ministry-backed regional coordination (CoPs and focal points) while progressing toward data governance and sharing frameworks.

How the challenges in Kenya, Malawi and Cameroon compare with other Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs)

Although this brief focuses on Kenya, Malawi, and Cameroon, the constraints observed at the middle tier are not unique to these three education systems.

Across many Low and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs), similar governance and capacity patterns, such as incomplete decentralisation, compliance-heavy workloads, resource scarcity, and limited analytical capability, shape whether subnational actors can use data for local decision-making and improvement ([↑Olsen et al., 2024](#)).

Table 1 summarises these recurring challenges, highlighting their common characteristics and system-level impacts.

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Table 1. *Four-pillar collaborative approach to strengthen middle-tier education data systems*

Findings	Characteristics	Impact
Incomplete (or reversed) decentralisation	<p>Power imbalance in which central governments largely retain control over funding, hiring, and policy.</p> <p>Examples – Kenya: middle-tier mandates can exceed capacity (e.g., counties expected to act, but tools/skills/resources lag).</p> <p>Malawi: ‘upward’ systems mean district-held cohort data can remain stuck below the central level.</p> <p>Cameroon: subnational convening can require explicit ministry approval and designated focal points before regional action is legitimised.</p>	<p>The middle tier is seen as an implementer rather than a partner.</p> <p>Resulting inequities (e.g., in the distribution of teachers and infrastructure) persist because data-driven local problem-solving is constrained.</p> <p>Devolution policies are not fully implemented and contextualised</p> <p>Local leaders sometimes interfere with educational management, particularly in matters of teacher transfers, promotions, and discipline.</p>
Process over pedagogy	<p>Dominance of administrative tasks, compliance reporting, and process management.</p> <p>Examples – Kenya: heavy reporting demands from various stakeholders lead to compliance over quality.</p> <p>Malawi: manual record-keeping burdens at school/zonal levels drive demand for digitisation rather than deeper learning analysis.</p> <p>Cameroon: early CoP attempts showed that stakeholders remained in camps, requiring additional groundwork before collaborative problem-solving could occur.</p>	<p>Administrative tasks dominate while learning and teaching innovations are sidelined.</p>

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Resource scarcity	<p>Insufficient and inflexible funding with little to no discretionary budgets.</p> <p>Subnational officers are expected to conduct quality assurance and classroom observations, among other duties, but there are no accompanying budget lines to support these mandates.</p> <p>Weak or no authority over budgets</p> <p>Examples — Kenya: scaling dashboards beyond pilot counties raises resourcing demands for onboarding and maintenance. Malawi: delays in funds can stall planned capacity activities even when technical design work is ready.</p>	<p>No flexible funds for experimentation.</p> <p>Resources not matching policy, e.g., capitation v free basic education, number of children v trained teachers</p>
Limited capacity, training and collaboration	<p>Insufficient Training in education governance, instructional leadership, or scaling innovations; little to no formal peer learning or knowledge-sharing; Upward data reporting, not for local decision-making.</p> <p>Examples — Kenya: capacity-building is being pursued through evidence synthesis training and revisions to quality assurance tools. Malawi: stakeholders requested digitisation and district- and school-level training to address practical bottlenecks in cohort tracking. Cameroon: CoP members demonstrated a limited understanding of evidence concepts (questions → indicators → actions), prompting targeted training.</p>	<p>Siloed efforts, no peer learning networks.</p> <p>Kenya: Mandates that don't align with capacity can deepen compliance behaviour and weaken sustained data use.</p>

A fragmented data ecosystem

Our engagement with the middle tier highlights that their education data management is characterised by fragmentation, insecurity, and underutilisation, hence crippling evidence-based decision-making. Too often, the same data is requested by different actors at the national level, increasing the risk of duplication and manipulation based on perceived use. The fragmentation manifests in at least four recurring facets across Kenya, Malawi, and Cameroon.

1. **Financial, personnel, and skills Crisis:** The middle tier lacks dedicated data clerks, analysts, and statisticians. Existing staff often lack the requisite skills in basic software and data analysis, leading to a 'data collection for compliance' culture rather than data use for insight and implementation.

In Kenya, this shows up as the need to first harmonise indicators and tools across counties before dashboards can be operationalised across multiple counties and linked to the national platform.

In Malawi, capacity constraints at the subnational level have limited the aggregation of data for analysis at the district and national levels. In addition, data remain siloed within districts and often within individual schools, preventing systematic analysis of pupil flow and progression across the primary education system.

In Cameroon, early findings from the Community of Practice in the North West Region indicate that many stakeholders, especially those in the field, lack an understanding of basic data concepts. What is good data? How is data collected?, why is data collected, and how is data used? In contrast, the results from the Community of Practice in the Centre region showed that stakeholders have the understanding and capacity to use data; however, the issue in this region is the intentional, high-level data manipulation for political and other reasons.

2. **Integrity and reporting Failures:** Deliberate data falsification is reported, often motivated by the perceived consequences of accurate reporting. Datasets often change depending on the intended use of the data generator. Coupled with poor report-writing capacity and missed deadlines, this erodes trust in data. In practice, low trust then reinforces 'upward reporting' behaviour, data is submitted to comply, not to enable local problem-solving at the district/county/regional level.
3. **Insecure and Inefficient Storage:** Data retrieval is cumbersome. Storage is often ad hoc and insecure, with overreliance on personal email and unofficial

channels due to the lack of enforcement of official government domains. The lack of backup systems and hardware creates a high risk of data loss.

4. Pervasive Data Gaps: Duplication of effort is rampant as schools are asked for the same data by multiple entities (Ministry, ministry agencies, NGOs/CSOs). The unharmonised, request-based collection tools and the non-standardised data-collection timeline yield low-quality, missing, and fragmented data.

For example, Kenya's dashboard work required an explicit tool/indicator harmonisation step because multiple parallel tools undermined consistency and usability.

In Malawi, harmonisation conversations have emerged around EMIS/cohort-tracking tools across different levels, as districts may end up using tools that do not cleanly align with the national system.

In Cameroon, the team shifted from *“one big convening”* to structured pre-consultations precisely because coordination and shared understanding were prerequisites for collective action.

Root causes of the challenges

These operational symptoms are driven by deeper systemic issues:

- Cultural and motivational: Ministries of education and their agencies are reluctant to provide data, often due to past experiences where data was used for punitive rather than supportive measures. In an environment where the value of data is not demonstrated, there exists a 'low attitude towards data'.
- Coordination Failure: The absence of a unified framework leads to multiple, uncoordinated data requests from various government and non-governmental organisations, overburdening schools and creating conflicting datasets. This coordination challenge also weakens trust – when different actors demand different numbers, the middle tier cannot confidently defend which dataset is 'official.'
- Chronic under-investment: Systemic neglect of the capacity in the data value chain from collection to analysis, learning and feedback is evident in the lack of dedicated personnel with administrative overload to the existing officers, training, software, licenses, and the appropriate accompanying hardware.

Proposed collaborative solutions

Addressing these challenges requires a concerted joint commitment of both the central and middle-tier levels of governance:

The goal is not isolated pilots, but a coherent package that improves (i) infrastructure, (ii) skills, (iii) governance, and (iv) resourcing – so that middle-tier actors can reliably collect, store, share, and use data for foundational learning decisions.

Table 2 summarises the four-pillar approach and illustrates how work in Kenya, Malawi, and Cameroon aligns with these pillars under the Unlocking Data initiative.

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Table 2. *Four-pillar collaborative intervention to strengthen middle-tier education data systems (Kenya, Malawi, Cameroon)*

Pillar	Proposed action	What are we doing under the Unlocking Data initiative?
Centralised data infrastructure	Strengthening and securing cloud-based Education management information systems (EMIS) with role-based access for the various stakeholders. Enforce the mandatory use of government email for official communications.	<p>In Malawi, the UDI is strengthening the EMIS by piloting cohort tracking in two districts. In Kenya, the revision of the EMIS is underway, and a research hub is being created within the Ministry.</p> <p>In Cameroon, the approach is being shaped through ministry-approved regional coordination (CoPs and focal points) and the exploration of DHIS2-style tooling as part of the pathway toward a usable subnational data system.</p>
Capacity building	Roll out a continuous subnational data fellowship program targeting county data officers on the purpose and use of data. This includes peer learning across the subnational level.	<p>Formation of communities of learning at the subnational level.</p> <p>Establishment of an evidence synthesis academy in Kenya with participation from subnational officers. Training of subnational officers and foundational learning teachers in curriculum interpretation and development of assessment tools. Training of teachers in numeracy error identification, analysis, and incorporation into classroom practice in Kenya, Nigeria, and South Africa, as well as on assessment, including the development of assessment items that teachers can tap into.</p>

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In Malawi, subnational engagement on cohort tracking has informed the design of targeted training and support linked to digitisation and improved data usability at school and district levels. In parallel, an Evidence Synthesis Academy has recently been launched, through which participants have been trained in conducting systematic reviews. In addition, postgraduate students from different schools at the University of Malawi (UNIMA) have been supported through capacity-building initiatives focused on using secondary education data, data analysis, software applications, and academic writing and publishing.

In Cameroon, CoP members identified gaps in understanding ‘what evidence is’ and how to move from questions to indicators; the team is organising evidence synthesis training (online + in-person, with an education-focused in-person component).

Enhanced data governance and sharing

Co-create subnational education databases and data sharing protocols to harmonise collection tools, define standard timelines (e.g., termly), and eliminate duplicate requests. Establish a feedback loop in which submitted data is analysed and results are shared back with the subnational.

Localised education dashboards in Kenya and Malawi at the subnational level. Partnerships with Universities to identify priority research areas where there are data and evidence gaps.

In Cameroon, ministry-backed regional CoPs (including designated focal points) are being used to validate a learning agenda and map available evidence, and the CoP has prioritised developing a data-sharing framework as one of its agreed actions.

Strategic Investment

Hire dedicated data management officers, invest in data collection and analysis, software, secure storage and basic hardware such as computers.

Across all three countries, this pillar is the ‘make it real’ constraint: without funded roles and maintained systems, harmonised tools, training, and protocols do not stick at the subnational level.

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Kenya: scaling interest beyond the pilot counties implies resourcing needs for onboarding/maintenance of the dashboard approach.

Malawi: the pace of implementation is sensitive to resourcing flows (e.g., delays stall planned district-level activities). Cameroon: Discussions with HISP (Health Information Systems Program) indicate potential fees for technical support and training related to the [DHIS2-Ed](#) platform.¹ As DHIS2-Ed offers an opportunity to modernise education data systems, enhance tracking of foundational learning outcomes, and improve data-informed planning in the education sector, the team is negotiating to secure affordable, sustainable support arrangements.

¹ See <https://dhis2.org/education/>.

Conclusion

The cost of failing to utilise the potential of the middle tier is ongoing inefficiency, wasted resources, and policy and planning not guided by reliable evidence. By investing collaboratively in a unified data system, the ministries of education and the middle tier can unlock the true potential of education data to support targeted interventions, track the education system's progress, and ultimately ensure better learning outcomes for every child.

References

This reference is available digitally in our evidence library at

<https://docs.edtechhub.org/lib/598VMI5J>

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